

Synthesis, molecular and crystalline architectures and properties of a cobalt(II) thiocyanate complex containing an *in situ* generated didentate Schiff base

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Abstract : One hexacoordinated mononuclear cobalt(II) thiocyanate compound of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{LL})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ (**1**) [LL = phenyl(pyridin-2-yl)methanimine] is isolated using a 1 : 2 : 2 : 2 molar ratio of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2-aminopyridine (ap), 2-benzoylpyridine (bp) and NH_4NCS in methanol at room temperature. The compound has been characterized using microanalytical, spectroscopic, magnetic, X-ray crystallographic and other physicochemical results. It is a non-electrolyte and behaves as a three-electron paramagnet. X-Ray structural study reveals that in the condensation reaction of ap and bp, some kind of degradation occurs in presence of the metal ion to afford an *in situ* generated didentate Schiff base (LL) in the complexed form. Cobalt(II) center in **1** has a distorted octahedral environment with a CoN_6 chromophore. Four N atoms of two LL units along with two N atoms of two terminal thiocyanates in mutual *cis* orientation are coordinated to the metal center. The mononuclear units in **1** are engaged in weak C-H...S hydrogen bonds and $\pi \dots \pi$ interactions promoting supramolecular dimensionality. Compound **1** shows reasonable thermal stability and exhibits $\pi \dots \pi^*$ fluorescence in solid state at room temperature.

Keywords : Cobalt(II) thiocyanate, *in situ* generated Schiff base, X-ray structure, thermal behavior, luminescence property.

Introduction

Research on design and synthesis^{1,2} of mono-, di- and polynuclear coordination compounds of cobalt(II), a $3d^7$ system, continues unabated because of their interesting synthetic, structural, spectroscopic and magnetic features³⁻⁶. Single-pot reaction of metal-ions, organic ligands and inorganic/organic terminals/bridges in pre-assigned molar ratios is a popular synthetic approach to afford compounds with tunable properties. In contrast, syntheses involving *in situ* unusual ligand preparation⁷⁻¹⁰ in presence of different metal ions, which are very much efficient for the isolation of stable metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) with exciting properties, are rare. Thiocyanate¹¹⁻¹⁴, a heterotriatomic molecular ion rod, is now being used to isolate different functional coordination compounds due to their versatile terminal/bridging motifs. Keeping in mind the various *in situ* preparation⁷⁻¹⁰ of Schiff bases, we wish to study such reaction in presence of cobalt(II) in combination with thiocyanate. One mononuclear cobalt(II) compound $[\text{Co}(\text{LL})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ (**1**) has been isolated using a 1 : 2 : 2 : 2 molar ratio of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2-aminopyridine

(ap), 2-benzoylpyridine (bp) and NH_4NCS . X-Ray structural study reveals that in the condensation reaction of ap and bp some degradation occurs to afford a didentate Schiff base (LL, Scheme 1). The details of synthesis, molecular and crystalline architectures, and properties of **1** are described below.

Scheme 1. Framework of LL with (N^i, N^p) donor set.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

Mononuclear $[\text{Co}(\text{LL})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ (**1**) was obtained by the reaction of a 1 : 2 : 2 : 2 molar ratio of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2-aminopyridine (ap), 2-benzoylpyridine (bp) and NH_4NCS in MeOH at room temperature. A condensation reaction between ap and bp followed by a degradation process in presence of cobalt(II) occurs to afford a didentate Schiff base L in **1**. X-Ray structural analysis confirms

this. The reaction is reproducible, as is evident from repetitive microanalytical and spectral results. The reproducibility reflects an inherent tendency towards formation of the complex **1**. The reaction is summarized in eq. (1) :

The new complex was characterized by microanalytical (C, H and N), spectroscopic, thermal and other physicochemical results. The microanalytical data are in good conformity with the formulation **1**. The moisture-insensitive complex is stable over long periods of time in powdery and crystalline states. It is soluble in organic solvents like methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. In MeCN solution compound **1** behaves a non-electrolyte, as reflected from its low conductivity value ($6 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)¹⁵. Room temperature solid-phase magnetic susceptibility measurement shows **1** to be three-electron ($3d^7$ high spin; $S = 3/2$) paramagnet with μ_{eff} value ~ 3.8 BM expected from discrete and magnetically non-coupled mononuclear compound.

In situ generation of L :

Structural analysis of compound **1** reveals the presence of a didentate Schiff base (L). It may be assumed that in the condensation reaction of ap and bp some degradation process^{8,10} occurs in presence of cobalt(II) to result in this Schiff base. A possible path may be portrayed (Scheme 2) in which elimination of the pyridine ring followed by protonation may presumably occur.

Scheme 2. Probable steps of the *in situ* reaction to afford LL in **1**.

Spectroscopic studies :

The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}) + (\text{C}=\text{C})$ stretching frequencies of the metal bound Schiff base are observed at 1624 and 1592 cm^{-1} . $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching vibration of the thiocyanate ap-

pears as a single and strong stretch at 2091 cm^{-1} ; the position of signal strongly suggests N-coordination of the pseudohalide¹⁶. $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ stretching frequency is noticed at 778 cm^{-1} . Orange-red solution of the complex shows a distinct strong and broad absorption band at 524 nm, characteristic of distorted octahedral cobalt(II) center; the transition is assignable to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ type¹⁷. The band at 266 nm may be assigned to a ligand-based charge transfer transition¹⁸.

Crystal structure of 1 :

The didentate Schiff base (LL) belongs to an unsymmetrical (N^i, N^p) ($\text{N}^i =$ imine N; $\text{N}^p =$ pyridine N) type of ligand. Complex of the type $[\text{M}(\text{N}^i, \text{N}^p)_2(\text{X})_2]$ ($\text{X} = \text{NCS}$, a heteroatomic pseudohalide) can, in principle, give rise to fifteen molecular architectures considering geometric isomers and linkage isomers (Scheme 3). Hence to expose the molecular architecture and to define the long-range crystalline architecture, single crystal X-ray structure determination of compound **1** was done. Structure analysis reveals that crystal lattice of **1** consists of mononuclear $[\text{Co}(\text{N}^i, \text{N}^p)_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ unit. Cooperative intermolecular C-H...S hydrogen bonds and $\pi \cdots \pi$ interactions in **1** result in 3D network structure. ORTEP diagram with atom labeling schemes and perspective views of the supramolecular structures are shown in Figs. 1–3. Selected bond distances and angles relevant to the coordination sphere are listed in Table 1. The relevant non-covalent bonds and interaction parameters are set in Tables 2 and 3.

The coordination polyhedron around cobalt(II) is best described as a distorted octahedron with a CoN_6 chromophore (Fig. 1). Distortion from the ideal octahedral geometry is due to asymmetric nature of the didentate Schiff base and the deviation of the refined angles ($90^\circ/180^\circ$) at the metal center. The coordination includes two chelated unsymmetrical didentate ligands coordinated by two N^i and two N^p atoms along with two terminal N^t ($\text{N}^t =$ thiocyanate N) atoms of the two thiocyanates in mutual *cis* orientation. Two pyridine N^p atoms ($\text{N}1, \text{N}1a$) of two different Schiff bases along with two terminal thiocyanate N^t atoms ($\text{N}3, \text{N}3a$) occupy the equatorial sites, and the two remaining imine N^i atoms ($\text{N}2, \text{N}2a$) of two LL units are in axial positions with bond angle $178.88(14)^\circ$. The two (N^i, N^p) units bite cobalt(II) center with Co-N distances 2.135(3)–2.172(3) Å. These are greater than Co- N^t distances [2.046(4) Å] reflecting the

Scheme 3. Possible geometrical and linkage isomers in $[\text{Co}(\text{N}^{\text{I}}, \text{N}^{\text{P}})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ (**1**).

Fig. 1. The fundamental coordination unit in **1** with atom numbering schemes.

strongest coordination of the anionic N^{I} centers of the thiocyanates over the neutral N^{I} and N^{P} centers of LL. It is of note that the distortion from ideal octahedral coordi-

nation is very significant from the ranges of *cisoid* $[74.04(11)^\circ - 106.85(11)^\circ]$ and *transoid* $[159.74(13)^\circ - 178.88(14)^\circ]$ angles, which show sufficient deviation from

Fig. 2. Hydrogen bonded two-dimensional (4,4) sheet structure in **1** formed by C-H...S interactions along *ab*-plane.

Fig. 3. 3D network structure in **1** formed by cooperative C-H...S hydrogen bonds and $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions.

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for **1**

Bond distances			
Co1-N1 ^a	2.172(3)	S1-C13	1.626(4)
Co1-N2 ^a	2.135(3)	C13-N3	1.149(5)
Co1-N3 ^a	2.046(4)		
Bond angles			
N3-Co1-N3 ^a	100.2(2)	N2 ^a -Co1-N1 ^a	74.04(11)
N3-Co1-N2	89.99(12)	N3-Co1-N1	159.74(13)
N3 ^a -Co1-N2	89.29(13)	N3 ^a -Co1-N1	92.10(13)
N3-Co1-N2 ^a	89.29(13)	N2-Co1-N1	74.04(11)
N3 ^a -Co1-N2 ^a	89.99(12)	N2 ^a -Co1-N1	106.85(11)
N2-Co1-N2 ^a	178.88(14)	N1 ^a -Co1-N1	81.05(17)
N3-Co1-N1 ^a	92.10(13)	N2-Co1-N1 ^a	106.85(11)
N3 ^a -Co1-N1 ^a	159.74(13)	N3-C13-S1	178.7(4)

Symmetry code : $a = -x, y, 1/2-z$.

Table 2. Hydrogen bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for **1**

D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A
C1-H1...S1 ⁱ	0.93	2.87	3.786(4)	168

Symmetry code : $i = -1/2+x, -1/2+y, z$.

Table 3. $\pi\cdots\pi$ Interaction parameters (Å, °) for **1**

Cg-Cg	Cg-Cg distance	Dihedral angle (<i>i, j</i>)	Perpendicular distances between baricenters (<i>i, j</i>)
Cg(4)-Cg(4) ⁱⁱ	4.754(3)	0.00	3.451(2)

Symmetry code : $ii = 1/2-x, 3/2-y, 1-z$.
Cg(4) = C(7)→C(8)→C(9)→C(10)→C(11)→C(12).

the ideal values (90°/180°). The sum (347.39°) of the equatorial angles [N3-Co1-N3^a 100.2(2)°, N3-Co1-N1^a 92.1(13)°, N1^a-Co1-N1 81.05(17)° and N2-Co1-N1 74.04(11)°] is closed to 360°. This reflects that the equatorial N atoms and metal center are almost in a same plane. Two terminal thiocyanates are almost linear [S1-C13-N3 178.7(4)] and mutually in *cis* alignment with Co-N-C bond angles close to 180° [Co1-N3-C13 175.5(3)°] (Table 1). The N3-C13 [1.149(5) Å] and S1-C13 [1.626(4) Å] bond lengths are as expected for N-coordination¹¹. The overall analysis reveals that **1** adopts the molecular architecture with a *cis, trans, cis* orientation of the three sets of donor centers in the order (N^p, N^p), (Nⁱ, Nⁱ) and (N^t, N^t).

In the crystal packing the S atom (S1) of terminal thiocyanate and *ortho*-hydrogen atom (H1) of pyridine ring of LL are engaged in weak doubly C-H...S hydrogen bonds (Table 2) resulting in a 2D (4,4) sheet structure (Fig. 2) along *ab*-plane. These 2D sheets in turn are further engaged in $\pi\cdots\pi$ interaction (Table 3) between benzene rings [Cg(4)-Cg(4)] of different molecular units resulting in a 3D network structure (Fig. 3).

Thermal behavior :

Thermogravimetric and differential thermal analyses (TG-DTA) were carried out to examine thermal stability of the compound. The sample made from crushed single crystals was heated between 40 and 800 °C in the static atmosphere of dinitrogen at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The TG curve (Fig. 4) shows that **1** is stable up to 194 °C. The compound loses one LL and two thiocyanate (obsd. : 54.7%; calcd. : 55.23%) in the first step of its decomposition. The second step weight loss (obsd. :

Fig. 4. Thermal behavior of **1**.

28.14%; calcd. : 33.74%) is in line with the removal of another LL moiety. The final residue may be due to one CoO unit (obsd. : 14.77%; calcd. : 13.85%).

Luminescence behavior :

The photoluminescence behavior of the complex **1** was examined in solid state at room temperature. Upon excitation of the solid sample at its maximum absorption band (320 nm) an emission band (Fig. 5) centered at 429 nm along with a small peak at 457 nm is observed, which may presumably be due to the ligand-based $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition^{19,20}.

Fig. 5. Fluorescence behavior of **1** in solid state.

Conclusion

In summary, one cobalt(II) thiocyanate compound con-

taining an *in situ* generated didentate Schiff base (LL) has been isolated. X-Ray structural study shows that the molecular architecture of **1** consists of a *cis, trans, cis* orientation of the three sets of donor centers in the order (N^p,N^p), (Nⁱ,Nⁱ) and (N^t,N^t), and the innocent zero-dimensional (0D) mononuclear units in **1** behave as supramolecular synthons promoting dimensionality to 3D via cooperative intermolecular C-H...S hydrogen bonds and $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions. The compound is thermally stable and is a good example of luminous material.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 2-benzoylpyridine (Lancaster, UK), 2-aminopyridine (Spectrochem, India), ammonium thiocyanate (Merck, India) and cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (E. Merck, India) were purchased from respective concerns and used as received. All other chemicals and solvents used were AR grade. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air. Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–400 cm^{-1}) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Molar conductances were measured using a Systronics conductivity meter where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01 (M) KCl solution, and MeCN was used as solvent. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility of powdered sample was mea-

sured on a CAHN electrobalance 7550 with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as a reference and diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants²¹. Thermal behaviors were examined with a Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DT analyzer heated from 40–800 °C under nitrogen. Ground state absorptions measurements (in MeCN) were made with a Shimadzu model UV-2450 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Solid state fluorescence measurements were done using a Perkin-Elmer LS55 fluorescence spectrometer.

Preparation of $[\text{Co}(\text{LL})_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ (**1**) :

To a $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.365 g, 1 mmol) solution in MeOH (10 ml), 2-aminopyridine (0.188 g, 2 mmol) and 2-benzoyl pyridine (0.366 g, 2 mmol) dissolved each in the same solvent (10 ml) were added dropwise. To this solution mixture, a solution of NH_4NCS (0.152 g, 2 mmol) in the same solvent (10 ml) was added. The final deep red solution was left undisturbed in an open air for slow evaporation. The microcrystals of **1** that deposited after a week were collected by filtration and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield : 0.404 g (75%). Found : C, 57.5; H, 3.8; N, 15.4%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{Co}$ (**1**) : C, 57.8; H, 3.7; N, 15.6; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}) + (\text{C}=\text{C})$ 1624, 1592; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ 2091; UV-Vis (MeCN, $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$) : 266, 524; Λ_{M} (MeCN, $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) : 6.

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

Single crystal of **1** suitable for X-ray analysis was selected from those obtained by slow evaporation of methanolic solutions at room temperature. Diffraction data were collected on a Bruker SMART APEX-II CCD area-detector diffractometer (296 K) using graphite monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The detector frames were integrated by use of the program SAINT²² and absorption corrections were performed with SADABS²³. The structures were solved by direct methods, using the SHELXTL²⁴ program. All atomic displacement parameters for non-hydrogen atoms have been refined with anisotropic term. For all structures, the hydrogen atoms were fixed geometrically and refined using a riding model. All calculations were carried out using SHELXTL, PLATON²⁵ and ORTEP-3²⁶ programs. Further details are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Crystallographic data and structure refinement parameters for **1**

Crystallographic parameters :	
Chemical formula	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{Co}$
Formula mass	539.53
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	C2/c
<i>a</i> (Å)	13.9135(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	10.5626(3)
<i>c</i> (Å)	17.9065(4)
α (°)	90.00
β (°)	109.149(3)
γ (°)	90.00
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	2485.98(10)
<i>T</i> (K)	296(2)
λ (Å)	0.71073
<i>Z</i>	8
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.771
ρ_{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	2.883
<i>F</i> (000)	2216
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.19 × 0.06 × 0.04
θ ranges (°)	2.41 to 25.57
<i>h</i> / <i>k</i> / <i>l</i>	-16,16/-12,12/-20,21
Reflections collected	19221
Independent reflections	2321
<i>T</i> _{max} and <i>T</i> _{min}	0.9325 and 0.7296
Data/restraints/parameters	2331/0/160
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.064
Final <i>R</i> ₁ values (<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>))	0.0505
Final <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²) values (<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>))	0.1399
Final <i>R</i> ₁ values (all data)	0.0766
Final <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²) values (all data)	0.1716
Goodness of fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.138
Largest peak and hole (e Å ⁻³)	0.449 and -0.683
Weighting scheme : $R = \frac{\sum F_o - F_c }{\sum F_o }$, $wR = \frac{[\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2]}{\sum w(F_o^2)^2}]^{1/2}$. Calcd. $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.1000P)^2 + 0.0000P]$ where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$, for 1 .	

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center Nos. 1006368 (**1**). Copies of this information can be obtained free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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